

NMTC- BEREKUM/ ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- DECEMBER 2016
D17 AND RM12 RGN 313 MEDICAL NURSING III
TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HOURS
ESSAY

Instructions

- *Answer all questions*
- *Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet*
- *Each question carries 20 marks.*
- *Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers*
- *Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will attract any mark*

Question One

Mr. Osei Tutu, 30 year old man is admitted to the male medical ward with Nephrotic Syndrome.

- a. Explain nephrotic syndrome to a first year Nursing student - 2mrks
 - b. Describe the pathophysiology of his condition - 7mrks
- describe the nursing management of Mr.Osei under the following
- i. diet - 5mrks
 - ii. Observations - 5mrks

Question Two

Adama Musah, 45yr old woman was admitted to Kofikrom hospital with the diagnosis of Gout.

- a. List **four(4)** factors that contributes to the development of Gout - 4mrks
- b. Mention **four(4)** diagnostic investigations of her condition - 4mrks
- c. Enumerate **five(5)** clinical manifestations that the patient will present - 5mrks
- d. State **seven (7)** pain management of this condition - 7mrks

Question Three

Madam.Akua,60 year old woman was admitted to the female medical ward with provisional diagnosis of osteoporosis.

- a. List **six(3)** signs and symptoms of her condition - 6mrks
- b. State **seven(7)** nursing management of Madam Akua - 7mrks
- c. Mention the **four(4)** types or classification of prostatitis - 4mrks
- d. Enumerate **three(3)** complications of prostatitis - 3mrks

HFNMTC-BEREKUM/ ST. MARY'S AMPUS – DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION - DECEMBER 2017

RGN 18 - MEDICAL NURSING III

TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HR.

ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

Question One

Mr. Michael Akuffo, a 35 year old carpenter is admitted to the male medical ward with a history of numbness and tingling sensation of the extremities. He has been diagnosed on having TYPE 1 Diabetes mellitus. He is on Insulin lente.

- a. Mention **THREE (3)** factors leading to the development of Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus - 3 marks
- b. State **THREE (3)** cardinal manifestation of the conditions and state why each of them occur - 6 marks
- c. Describe the care you will give to Mr. Akuffo under the following
 - i. Diet - 6 marks
 - ii. Insulin Therapy - 5 marks

Question Two

Master Emmanuel Appiah, a 15 year old student is admitted to the medical ward with diagnosis of nephrotic syndrome.

- a. Mention **EIGHT (8)** clinical manifestations of nephrotic syndrome - 4 marks
- b. What nursing interventions would you give regarding the following
 - i. Fluid overload - 3 marks
 - ii. Nutrition - 4 marks
 - iii. Education on discharge - 5 marks
- c. List **FOUR (4)** complications of nephrotic syndrome - 4 marks

Question Three

Mr. Kwadwo Nkansah, 70 years is on your ward with gout.

- a. Outline **SIX(6)** Risk factors of Mr. Nkansah's illness - 3marks
- b. Describe the pathophysiology of gout - 4marks
- c. State how you will manage Mr. Nkansah with regards to:
 - i. Provision of comfort - 6marks
 - ii. Diet - 4marks
- d. Mention three (3) complications of gout - 3marks

NMTC - BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- DECEMBER 2015
RGN 16 HRGN 080 MEDICAL NURSING III
TIME ALLOWED: 2HRS
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers

Not that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

A 30 year -old man was rushed into your emergency ward with the complain of joint pain, and was diagnosed as having gout.

- a. List five (5) risk factors of this condition. - 5marks
- b. mention four(4) laboratory investigations that are needed to be done on this condition - 2marks
- c. Mention ten (10) signs and symptom that the patient may exhibit - 5marks
- . State four nursing management each under the following
 - ii. pain - 4marks
 - i. diet - 4marks

Question Two

Mr. Menasha a 50 year old man reported to the medical ward with a provisional diagnosis of acute pancreatitis.

- a. How would you explain "acute pancreatitis" to a junior nurse in the ward - 3 marks
- b. Mention ten (10) signs and symptoms of this condition - 5 marks
- c. As a nurse on duty mention five dietary management of Mr. Menasha - 5 marks
- d. State three (3) medical management of Mr. Menasha - 3 marks
- e. Mention four risks factors that can bring about this condition - 4 marks

Question Three

. Kofi, a 40 year- old was admitted to your ward with a diagnosis of encephalitis.

- a. How will you explain the pathophysiology of this condition in not more than 30 words to a first year student?- 6 marks
- b. Briefly explain the two(2) types of encephalitis - 4marks
- c. Mention six (6) specific neurological signs and symptoms of this condition - 6 marks
- d. In your nursing assessment mention four (4) important nursing observations you will make on this patient - 4 marks

Question Four

- a. Mention four (4) important education you will give to a patient who is having prostatitis - 4marks
- b. State four (4) complications of prostatitis . - 4marks

Mr. Williamson, a 55-year old patient reported to the medical ward with provisional diagnosis of osteoporosis.

- c. How will you explain osteoporosis in to a colleague not more than 30 words. - 3marks
- d. Describe the pathophysiology of Mr. Williamson condition - 4marks
- e. Mention six (6) signs and symptoms of this condition - 6marks

INDEX NUMBER

HFNMTC- BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- MAY 2017

RM12 MEDICAL NURSING III

TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HRS

ESSAY

INSTRUCTION :

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will attract any mark

QUESTION ONE

Mr. Osei Tutu, 30 year old man is admitted to the male medical ward with Nephrotic Syndrome

- a. Explain nephrotic syndrome to a first year Nursing student - 2mrks
- b. Describe the pathophysiology of his condition - 8mrks
- c. Describe the nursing management of Mr. Osei under the following
 - i. diet - 5mrks
 - ii. observations - 5mrks

QUESTION TWO

A 25 year old man, Kofi Totobi, a known diabetic patient was brought to the emergency ward with diabetic keto acidosis(DKA)

- a. List the three(3) causes of diabetic ketoacidosis(DKA) - 3mrks
- b. list ten(10) clinical manifestation of his condition - 6mrks
- c. State four(4) diagnostic measures of his condition - 4mrks
- d. describe the nursing management of Kofi Totobi - 7mrks

QUESTION THREE

Madam Owusu Akos, 60 years old was brought to the Holy Family Hospital, Berekum with Hemiparesis (weakness of arm and leg on the same side), hemiplegia and was diagnosed with cerebrovascular accident (stroke)(CVA).

- a. State the four(4) main causes of Madam Owusu's condition - 4mrks
- b. List six (6) modifiable factors that contribute to the development of CVA. - 3mrks
- c. Discuss the nursing management of her condition under the following
 - i. Nutrition - 6mrks
 - ii. Observations - 7mrks

NMTC - BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION - DECEMBER 2012
(D13) HRGN 080 MEDICAL NURSING III
TIME ALLOWED:- 2 Hrs.
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

Madam Larteley Adam is on admission with the diagnosis of acute renal failure on account of intake of herbal preparation for severe constipation which led to severe diarrhea. She is on peritoneal dialysis.

- a. How would you explain acute renal failure to a student nurse? - 7 marks
- b. Enumerate four (4) main postrenal causes of acute renal failure - 4 marks
- What would you tell a student nurse who wants to know why Madam Adam is on peritoneal dialysis? - 6 marks
- d. State six (6) complications of peritoneal dialysis - 3 marks

Question Two

Madam Ekua Danso, a business woman is on admission with a diagnosis of acute gout affection the big toe.

- a. State six (6) signs and symptoms that Madam Danso would present - 3 marks
- b. Describe the nursing interventions that would be implemented to relieve her pains - 10 marks
- c. Explain the education that would be given on nutrition - 5 marks
- d. List four (4) other conditions affecting metabolism - 2 marks

Question Three

Briefly, explain the following;

- i. Hyperthyroidism - 5 marks
- ii. Thyrotoxic Crisis (thyroid storm) - 5 marks
- iii. Ischemia - 2 marks
- iv. Retinopathy - 2 marks
- v. Pechromocytoma - 2 marks
- vi. Hypokalemia - 2 marks
- vii. Virilization - 2 marks

Question Four

- a. What is hyperthyroidism? - 2 marks
- b. Describe the pathophysiology of Thyrotoxicosis - 10 marks
- c. List two (2) permanent treatment modalities for Thyrotoxicosis - 2 marks
- d. State twelve (12) clinical features of Tabes Dorsalis - 6 marks

NMTC - BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION - NOVEMBER 2013
(D14) IIRGN 680 MEDICAL NURSING III
TIME ALLOWED: 2Hrs.
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
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- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

- a. Differentiate between hyperthyroidism and thyrotoxicosis - 4 marks
- b. Outline the pathophysiology of Toxic Goiter - 6 marks
- c. Give an outline of the management of Goiter - 10marks

Question Two

Madam Agyekum Sumala is diagnosed of renal failure

- a. State ten (10) prerenal causes of acute renal failure - 5 marks
- b. How will you manage this patient on diet - 5 marks
- c. Describe your nursing management of this patient regarding monitoring fluid and electrolyte balance - 10 marks

Question Three

- a. Describe how you will monitor and manage Addisonian Crisis - 10 marks
- b. Describe the condition Diabetes Mellitus, making a clear distinction between type I and II - 4 marks
- c. Describe the condition General paresis, also known as general paralysis of the insane or paralytic dementia and state six (6) clinical features of the condition - 6 marks

Question Four

Mr. Kuma reported to the out patient department of your hospital with acute Rheumatoid Arthritis

- a. List ten (10) clinical Manifestations of rheumatoid arthritis - 5 marks
- b. Describe the pathophysiology of rheumatoid arthritis - 4 marks
- c. What education will you give to Mr. Kuma before he goes home? - 4 marks
- d. Describe five (5) predisposing factors of Deep Vein Thrombosis - 5 marks

HFNMTC BEREKUM/ ST. MARY'S CAMPUS- DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – DECEMBER, 2018
(RGN 313) MEDICINE AND MEDICAL NURSING III
TIME ALLOWED: 2 HRS.

ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

Mr. Oponng, a 35-year old is admitted to your ward with diagnosed with Type II diabetes mellitus. She has developed diabetic ketoacidosis with blood glucose level of 33.3 mmol/L as a result of missing his insulin injection for the past 24 hours.

- a. List **EIGHT (8)** clinical manifestations of diabetic ketoacidosis - 4 marks
- b. Describe how you will administer insulin to Mr. Oponng (requirement not needed) - 7marks
- c. State the **FIVE (5)** classes of oral antidiabetic agents and **one (1) example** each used in managing type II diabetes - 5 marks
- d. Mention **EIGHT (8)** complications of diabetes mellitus - 4 marks

Question Two

Miss Peters, a 17 year old student is on admission at the female medical ward with a provisional diagnosis bacterial meningitis with a confirmation of positive Kernig's sign and Positive Brudzinski's sign.

- a. List **EIGHT (8)** risk factors associated with meningitis - 4 marks
- b. State **EIGHT (8) other** clinical signs and symptoms Miss. Peters is likely to present- 4 marks
- c. Describe the nursing care you will give to Miss. Peters till she is fully recovered - 10 marks
- d. List **FOUR (4)** complications of meningitis - 2 marks

Question Three

Miss Beatrice Ocloo, a 21-year-old SHS graduate, is on admission at your ward with diagnosis of Acute Renal Failure (ARF) due to post renal factor.

- a. Mention **SIX** post-renal causes of Acute Renal Failure - 3marks
- b. Outline **TEN** clinical manifestations of ARF - 5marks
- c. Describe her nursing management under:
 - i. Observation - 6marks
 - ii. Diet - 4marks
- d. State **FOUR** complications of ARF - 2marks

Question Four

Mr. Opare, 65 years old Cocoa farmer is on admission at your ward with Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA).

- a. Explain Rheumatoid Arthritis to a first-year student nurse. - 2marks
- b. State **TEN** clinical manifestations of RA - 5marks
- c. Describe the pathophysiology of RA - 5marks
- d. State **FOUR** nursing interventions for the following Nursing diagnoses
 - i. Acute pain related to swollen/inflamed joints - 4marks
 - ii. Knowledge deficit related to the risk factors, pathophysiology and management of RA. 4marks

INDEX NUMBER.....

HFNMTC- BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION, MAY 2021
RGN 21 MEDICAL NURSING III
TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HR
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will attract any mark.

QUESTION ONE

A 56-year-old woman is on admission at the female medical ward with a provisional diagnosis of bacterial meningitis with a confirmation of positive Kernig's sign and Positive Brudzinski's sign.

- a. List **EIGHT (8)** risk factors associated with meningitis - 4 marks
- b. State **EIGHT (8)** other clinical signs and symptoms likely to present - 4 marks
- c. Describe the nursing care you will render to her:
 - i. Before Lumber puncture - 5marks
 - ii. After Lumber puncture - 7marks

QUESTION TWO

Mrs. Koomson, 62 years old farmer is on admission at your medical ward with diagnosis of Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA).

- a. Explain Rheumatoid Arthritis to a first-year student nurse. - 2 marks
- b. State **TEN** clinical manifestations of RA - 5 marks
- c. Describe the pathophysiology of RA - 5 marks
- d. State **FOUR** nursing interventions for the following Nursing diagnoses
 - i. Acute pain related to swollen/inflamed joints - 4 marks
 - ii. Knowledge deficit related to the risk factors, pathophysiology and management of RA. - 4 marks

QUESTION THREE

- a. A woman with 32 weeks gestation is diagnosed with Acute Pyelonephritis.
 - i. Describe how you will collect mid-stream urine specimen for microbial investigation - 7 marks
 - ii. Educate a Senior High School young lady in your house on prevention of Pyelonephritis - 3 marks
- b. Mr. Kumah is a 64-year-old known diabetic patient on insulin is rushed to the emergency unit, suspected to have diabetic ketoacidosis (DKA).
 - i. Mention **TEN(10)** signs and symptoms likely to be manifested by Mr. Kumah - 5marks
 - ii. Describe the nursing management you would render to Mr Kumah before arrival of the doctor. - 5marks

